

Email engagement in leisure time and health and productivity

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Work-related stress is a key challenge for economies globally, with far-reaching individual, organisational and societal consequences. One contributor to work-related stress is the blurring of boundaries between work and home domains, known as work-home interference (WHI). A legacy of the COVID-19 pandemic is increased flexible and remote working, which could increase WHI and resultantly work-related stress. A tangible marker of WHI is employee engagement with work emails during leisure time, however very little is known about the prevalence, predictors, and impacts of this behaviour. In a sample of 1229 UK-based employees, we report on social norms and work-place culture around engaging with work emails outside of normal working hours. Additionally, we investigated whether work email importance, email overload and email management tactics were associated with email engagement during leisure time, and whether this type of email engagement was associated with health and productivity, in cross-section. Participants who reported that email was highly important and/or felt overloaded by emails were more likely to engage with work emails during leisure time. Additionally, email engagement in leisure time was associated with poorer physical and psychological health, but not productivity. Our findings have implications for organisational policy and culture around employee email engagement behaviours.

Keywords: email engagement; email overload; physical health; productivity; psychological health

Understanding the origins of, and contributors to, work-related stress is a key research area that has wide-reaching implications. To illustrate, in 2018/19 (the last data available pre COVID-19) there were 602,000 cases of work-related stress, depression or anxiety in the UK, which resulted in 12.8 million working days lost (HSE, 2019). Work-related stress increases risk for cardiovascular disease and muscular disorders, as well as increasing the impact and prevalence of mental health difficulties such as depression and anxiety (HSE, 2006). Thus, at an individual level, work-related stress is a significant risk for poor physical and mental health. There are also wider impacts of work-related stress, including social and economic costs. For example, it is estimated that the economic cost of work-related stress to the UK is £7–12.6 billion per year (Chandola, 2010), and the financial cost of mental ill health to British business is £26 billion per year, equivalent to £1,035 per employee (ERS, 2016). Similar effects are observed in other countries (Hassard et al., 2018). This key challenge has been recognised by the UK Government, and Public Health England have published an initiative entitled “Improving Work Health for a Healthy Economy” (PHE, 2017), which provides advice for business and includes a specific mental health toolkit for employers. Although there have been positive moves towards improving workplace health, there remains a high prevalence of work-related stress. One explanation is that technological advances over the past decade, particularly the use of smartphones and tablets, has resulted in an increase in non-standard work schedules, including evening, night and weekend work (Derks & Bakker, 2014; Harma, 2006; Jean-François et al., 2015; Tarafdar & Cooper, in press; Tarafdar et al., 2019). The focus of the present study is on exploring how the use of technology to access work-related messages, specifically through email, may impact health and productivity.

The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the trend towards remote working (Levanon, 2020), and there is an even greater reliance on this technology to remain connected to the workplace. Mobile devices, for example, are the most popular form of accessing emails, with around half of all emails being opened on mobile devices (Specht, 2018). The flexibility to enable people to balance work and family life has been highlighted as a positive in the Marmot Review (Fair Society, Healthy Lives, 2010). However, an unintended consequence of agile working may be a constraint to work, as French politician Benoit Hamon suggested, via an “electronic leash” (Schofield, 2016), and a resultant inability to “switch off” from work. Work-home interference (WHI) refers to a process of negative interaction between work and home domains (Van Hooff et al., 2006) and increasing expectations regarding availability suggest that employees feel compelled to immediately respond to work-related messages, even during leisure time (Davis, 2002). Such pressures may be both overt, with managers setting clear expectations to remain engaged with work via electronic communications, or more subtle and attributable to unspoken company norms or a desire to demonstrate a high work ethic. Individual motives to access email during leisure time may also be important. For example, some individuals may experience a positive emotional response after “clearing the inbox” (Barley et al., 2011).

While recognising that there are individual motivations to engage with email, employees who stay connected to their work during leisure time make it very hard, if not impossible, to psychologically detach from work, connect fully with family and social groups, thus increasing WHI and impeding rest and recovery (Derks & Bakker, 2014). Although several studies have investigated the effects of weekends and holidays on employee health and well-being, the beneficial effects of these relatively long periods away from work diminish quickly (Fritz & Sonnentag, 2005, 2006). In contrast, daily recovery during evening hours has a larger impact on employee health, well-being and productivity (Sonnentag, 2001, 2003). In support of these findings, self-reported stress during leisure time, but not during work hours, was significantly associated with hair cortisol, a biological marker of chronic stress levels (Gidlow et al., 2016). This association may reflect a general inability to rest and recover from work during leisure time, resulting in long-term effects via biological embedding of stress (Chandola et al., 2006).

To date, few studies have examined the specific role of engaging with work emails on perceived stress. One large cross-sectional survey of 471 University staff in Australia found that an expectation of a quick turnaround and an escalation in email traffic were associated with email overload and increased work-related stress (Pignata et al., 2015). There is also evidence from small observational studies that personality traits, such as worry, and longer time spent responding to emails are associated with increased perceived stress and reduced productivity (Jerejian et al., 2013; Mark et al., 2016). One small experimental study ($N = 124$) tested the effects of restricting the frequency of email checking to three times a day and reported that this had a positive impact on employee stress and well-being (Kushlev & Dunn, 2015). However, we have recently reported that a change in engaging

with work emails outside of normal working hours from pre-COVID to during-COVID was not associated with health and productivity in a small group of 92 employees who were exclusively working from home because of the COVID-19 restrictions (Braithwaite et al., 2023).

The varied findings from the few studies that have explored the specific role of engaging with work emails on perceived stress suggests it is a complex relationship. Typically, a transactional view of stress and coping sees stress occurring whenever the perceived demands of a situation tax, or exceed, the perceived resources of the person (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). This approach underpins the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model (Demerouti et al., 2001; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004) which provides a framework to understand the impact of engaging with email and its effects on health. Job demands are any aspect of the job that require sustained physical and/or psychological effort or skills, while job resources refer to those aspects of the job that are functional in achieving work goals, stimulating personal growth and/or reducing job demands (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). The model predicts that high demands can lead to strain and subsequent negative individual (health problems, burnout) and organizational (e.g. reduced performance, absence) outcomes due to the physical and psychological costs associated with coping with them (health impairment process). High resources can buffer the effect of high demands and trigger motivational processes which can lead to increased work engagement, wellbeing and performance outcomes (motivational pathway). If resources are low, this could contribute to the health impairment process of high job demands (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). However, email can be seen as both a demand (e.g., I need to be contactable 24/7) and a resource (e.g., I can keep on top of my work while away from the office). Given little is known about social norms and general levels of engagement with work emails outside of normal working hours, this provides the rationale for the present study as the first step in understanding how workers engage with email and the potential for emails to be both a demand and a resource.

We also recognise that there are many forms of electronic applications that can be used for work, even those which are most frequently used for social purposes (e.g., WhatsApp). However, the present study focuses on email because it is a salient work-related prompt that initiates work-related activity, and it is an objective variable that can be quantified. Further, email volume and feelings of email overload are associated with work-related stress levels (Jerejian et al., 2013; Pignata et al., 2015). Thus, we hypothesise that engaging with email during leisure time will increase WHI, impede rest, recovery and recuperation, resulting in poorer physical health, psychological health, and productivity.

An unintended consequence of agile working may be an increased pressure to be responsive to work emails at all hours, resulting in employees who feel constrained to work by an “electronic leash”. However, very little is known about social norms and general levels of engagement with work emails outside of normal working hours. Our research aims to explore, in individuals who do predominantly computer-based office work, the social norms around email engagement outside of working hours and examine how interacting with work emails during leisure time may impact physical health, psychological health, and productivity. This research is particularly important and timely because the world of work, and working practices, are changing post-COVID-19, with a greater move to remote working and flexible working, and the reliance on technology to facilitate this. Further, interventions targeted at email practices are already being implemented. For example, one way in which companies (e.g., Volkswagen; Daimler) and indeed countries (e.g., France) have sought to improve employee well-being and productivity is by challenging email practices (Braithwaite, 2018). Some companies now restrict “out of hours” access to emails, whereas others automatically delete emails received when an employee is on holiday. Yet, as a recent British Psychological Society report noted, many employees have not been provided with clear guidance and support on how best to manage mobile technology and access to work-related emails (Weinberg, 2017). Further, no empirical research has examined the direct link between engaging with work emails during leisure time and employee health and productivity, so it is currently unknown whether such changes in email practices could have the desired beneficial effects. The present research, therefore, had three primary aims: (1) Examine and report social norms around employee engagement with work emails outside of normal working hours; (2) Examine associations between email work importance, email management tactics, email overload and engagement with work emails during leisure time, and (3) Test associations between engagement with work emails during leisure time and physical health, psychological health, and productivity.

In line with our aims, we made the following three hypotheses which we pre-registered prior to data analysis (<https://osf.io/n7dya>): (1) Higher ratings of email work importance and email overload will

be associated with greater email engagement during leisure time; (2) A higher use of email management tactics will be associated with reduced email engagement during leisure time; (3) A high level of email engagement outside of normal working hours will be associated with poorer physical and psychological health, and lower productivity.

METHODOLOGY

Procedure

Data was derived from a cross-sectional survey, hosted by Qualtrics. Participants read a participant information sheet and provided informed consent prior to providing any survey data. The survey included questions on participant demographics, email culture and e-communications at their place of work, email strain, physical health, psychological health, and productivity. On completion of the survey, participants were provided with a debrief and thanked for their time. Data were collected between November 2020 and July 2022. Ethical approval for this research study was provided by the Manchester Metropolitan University (Ref 17726). The survey used in this research is available to view and download at <https://osf.io/xemvc/>.

Participants

We aimed to recruit a minimum of 1000 participants, to allow 95% power to detect medium effect sizes using linear regression models with an estimated number of 7 predictor variables. Participants were required to be at least 18 years of age, UK-based, and in full-time employment to participate in the survey. We used several methods to recruit potential participants to complete the survey, including: the prolific platform (www.prolific.com, $n=1017$), participants who completed an online Future Learn course on workplace health and wellbeing were invited to complete the survey ($n=260$), and we advertised the survey on several social media platforms (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Reddit $n = 65$). In total, $N = 1,342$ participants started the survey, of which $N = 1229$ completed the survey. Only participants who completed the survey were included in the data analysis. Of the 1229 participants who completed the survey, some cases did have missing data points, which we address in the Measures and Statistical Analysis sections. A post hoc power calculation indicated that with 1229 participants, we had 99.9% power to detect medium effect sizes ($f^2=0.15$) and 91.1% power to detect small effect sizes ($f^2 = 0.02$).

Measures

Demographics

The survey contained questions on demographic variables, including age, gender, ethnicity, education, type of employment (fixed term/permanent/contractor), level of position (Executive/Senior staff/ Professional/Technician/ Customer services, and Admin/Secretarial/Support staff, and other), and industry. Our survey included the following categories for industry: Healthcare, Finance and Banking, Construction, Information Technology, Manufacturing, Wholesale and Retail, Transport and Logistics, and Other (self-describe). A large proportion of participants ($N = 405$) chose "Other", and based on their self-descriptions, we added and categorised participants into the following categories where applicable: Defence and Security, Leisure, Travel and Tourism, Third Sector, Public Sector, Energy, Utilities and Environment, Hospitality, Legal and Law Enforcement.

Work-place e-mail culture

We asked participants to respond to several questions about workplace e-communications, including whether participants check emails whilst on annual leave (yes/no), whether they have access emails on personal mobile phone (yes/no), and whether they have responsibility for shared inboxes (yes/no). We also asked participants to respond to the following statements using a 5-point Likert-type scale from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree”: “There is an expectation in my workplace that I respond to work emails outside of my normal working hours”, “It is common within my workplace for staff to respond to emails outside of normal working hours”, “My line manager regularly emails me outside of my normal working hours”. Additionally, we asked participants to indicate whether they use video calls, instant messaging or social media to communicate with their colleagues outside of normal working hours (yes/no).

Email strain

The Email Strain Questionnaire (ESQ) was used to assess email behaviour, which has previously been reported to have a robust factor structure and good internal reliability (Dabbish & Kraut, 2006; Pignata et al., 2015). The ESQ generates two subscales: Email Work Importance containing 4 items (e.g., “Email is critical for getting my work done”), and Email Overload containing 7 items (e.g. “I find dealing with my emails overwhelming”). Items are rated using a Likert-type 5-point scale, where participants are required to indicate the extent that they agree with each statement, from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree”. The four email work importance items were averaged to create the email work importance variable. Four cases had one item missing on this scale, and one case had two missing data points; for these cases the work email importance score was calculated by averaging across the available data points. To create the email overload variables, items one, three and five were reverse-scored, and an average across the seven items was calculated. Sixteen cases had one missing item on this scale, and two cases had three missing items; for these cases the work email importance score was calculated by averaging across the available data points. The internal reliability was very good for the Email Work Importance (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.850) and the Email Overload (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.809) variables.

The ESQ also contains eight items on email management tactics, such as “I try to keep my inbox size small” and “I file my messages into separate folders.” Participants were required to indicate the extent that they agreed with each statement on a Likert-type 5-point scale from “Never” to “Always”. In the original study where these items were developed, the authors hypothesised that these items would load onto three factors: checking email, managing the inbox, and filing (Dabbish & Kraut, 2006). However, they did not find the factor structure that they expected, perhaps because their sample was underpowered ($N = 434$) (Dabbish & Kraut, 2006). With our data from over 1000 participants, we conducted an exploratory factor analysis and found the email management tactics items loaded onto two factors: filing emails and managing tasks. The items loaded onto the two factors as follows:

1. Filing emails

- a. I file my messages into separate folders
- b. I manually file my messages as soon as they come in
- c. I try to keep my inbox size small
- d. I keep messages in my inbox after I have read them (reverse scored)

2. Managing tasks

- a. I check my email as soon as I see or hear a new message has arrived
- b. I restrict myself to checking my email at specific times of the day (reverse scored)
- c. I keep messages in my inbox as a reminder of things I need to do

We therefore created a filing emails score (where higher scores indicate that the participant is more diligent with filing emails and managing their inbox) and a managing tasks score (where a higher score indicates that participants more regularly check emails and use it for managing work tasks) by averaging the items in each subscale. The filing emails subscale showed good internal reliability (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.740), however the managing tasks subscale showed poor internal reliability (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.441). The third item (I keep messages in my inbox as a reminder of things I need to do) correlated moderately with the other two items, however when removed the Cronbach’s

alpha only marginally improved (0.516). We therefore decided to only use the filing emails subscale in further analyses of email management tactics.

Email volume

In line with Pignata et al. (2015), we also asked participants to indicate the number of emails received in the past 24 hours (email volume), and the number of emails read and sent in the past 24 hours (summed to produce an email engagement variable) (Pignata et al., 2015). We additionally asked participants to indicate how many of those were received/read/sent outside of normal working hours. This resulted in the generation of four additional email-related variables: email volume, email volume outside of working hours, email engagement, and email engagement outside of working hours. We have previously used this approach to measure email volume and engagement (Braithwaite et al., 2023).

Physical and psychological health

We used the 17-item Physical and Psychological Health subscale from A Short Survey Assessment Tool (ASSET), which has previously demonstrated good construct validity (Johnson & Cooper, 2003). Participants were required to indicate the extent to which they have experienced different physical and psychological health symptoms over the past two weeks using a Likert-type 4-point scale from “Never” = 1 to “Often” = 4. The first six items relate to physical health and were summed to create a physical health variable which showed good internal reliability (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.756), and the remaining 11 items relate to psychological health and were summed to create a psychological health variable which showed very good internal reliability (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.927). On the physical health variable, five cases had one missing data point, and on the psychological health variable 14 cases had one missing data point, and one case had two missing data points. Missing data was imputed using an average of the available data points, and total scores were summed as above.

Productivity

Productivity of white-collar workers is difficult to measure (Schroeder Roger et al., 1985), we therefore took two approaches to measuring productivity in this survey. First, we used a 7-item presenteeism subscale from the World Health Organisation Health and Performance Questionnaire (HPQ) (Kessler et al., 2003). The HPQ is a self-report instrument designed to estimate the workplace costs of health problems in terms of reduced job performance, sickness absence and work-related accidents and injuries. The 7 items that we used refer to work level, accuracy, and concentration (key performance metrics of white-collar workers) and require participants to respond to statements about their working practices on a Likert-type 4-point scale from “Never” to “All of the time”. Items two to seven were reverse-scored, and an average calculated across items, to give a score of one to seven, where higher numbers indicate better productivity. One missing data point was present in N = 13 cases, and two cases had two missing data points; the average score was calculated from the available data. This scale showed good internal reliability (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.751). The second approach that we used to measure productivity was a single item adapted from ASSET (Faragher et al., 2004), which asks participants “Over the last month, roughly how productive have you felt in your job?”. Participants were required to respond using a visual analogue scale from 0% to 100%. We have previously used these two approaches to measuring productivity of white-collar workers (Braithwaite et al., 2023).

Statistical analysis

All subscales were calculated in accordance with published guidelines, and missing data was dealt with as described above. Outliers were identified and removed: two outliers were removed from the Email Volume variable, three from the Email Volume outside of normal working hours variable, three from the Email Engagement variable, and one from the Email Engagement outside of normal working hours variable. We then checked the distribution of all variables, and 4 variables were highly skewed and kurtosed: Email volume, Email volume outside of normal working hours, Email Engagement and Email Engagement outside of normal working hours. To deal with the skewed and kurtosed distribution we used square-root transformations, which normalised the distribution of these variables. All other variables were normally distributed.

To address aim 1 of the study, we descriptively reported on participant's email engagement behaviours, and social norms/culture around accessing work-based emails. To address aim 2, we conducted three linear regression models to examine associations between work email importance (independent variable), email overload (independent variable), email management tactics – filing emails (independent variable), and email engagement during leisure time (dependent variable). We accounted for the following potential confounding variables: participant age, gender, ethnicity, employment type, level of position, industry. All categorical variables were dummy coded before being entered into the regression models, with the following used as the reference value: male, white, full-time, executive, healthcare. To address aim 3 of the study, we conducted four linear regression models to examine associations between email engagement during leisure time (independent variable), and physical health (dependent variable), psychological health (dependent variable), productivity (dependent variable), and presenteeism (dependent variable). We accounted for the following potential confounding variables: participant age, gender, ethnicity, employment type, level of position, industry; categorical variables were dummy coded as described above. These hypotheses and analyses were pre-registered (<https://osf.io/n7bdya>).

Because email overload was strongly associated with health and productivity in correlation analyses, we conducted further exploratory analyses that were not pre-registered, and for which we had not a priori made hypotheses about analysis outcomes. We conducted four additional linear regression models to examine associations between email overload (independent variable), and physical health (dependent variable), psychological health (dependent variable), productivity (dependent variable), and presenteeism (dependent variable). We accounted for the following potential confounding variables: participant age, gender, ethnicity, employment type, level of position, industry; categorical variables were dummy coded as described above. The raw data (with the job title variable removed) is available to view and download (<https://osf.io/6zbgr/>). All data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics v25.

RESULTS

Descriptive characteristics

Descriptive characteristics of the sample are presented in Table 1. Mean age was 35.87 years (SD=10.03) and there was a good balance between male (46.2%) and female (53.1%) participants. 90.1% of the sample self-reported as white and participants indicated that they were generally highly educated, with 38.9% indicating that they had an undergraduate degree, and 24.4% reported that they had a post-graduate degree. The majority (81.2%) indicated that they were employed on a permanent contract, and 44.5% identified as professionals. A wide range of industries were represented, see Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the physical health, psychological health, presenteeism and productivity measures as also presented in Table 1.

Table 1
 Descriptive statistics of the sample

	<i>N</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Age	1133		35.87	10.03
Gender				
Female	652	53.1		
Male	568	46.2		
Non-Binary	3	0.2		
Trans	1	0.1		
Prefer not to say	4	0.3		
Ethnicity				
White	1106	90.1		
Mixed	26	2.1		
Asian	53	4.4		
Black	29	2.4		
Arab	2	0.2		
Other	10	0.8		
Highest Educational Qualification				
Post-graduate degree	297	24.4		
Undergraduate degree	474	38.9		
A level	234	19.2		
GCSE	116	9.5		
BTEC	35	2.9		
Diploma	63	5.2		
Employment type				
Fixed Term	187	15.3		
Permanent	991	81.2		
Contractor	43	3.5		
Position				
Executive	49	4		
Senior Staff	216	17.6		
Professional	545	44.5		
Technician	67	5.5		
Customer services	85	6.9		
Admin/Secretarial/Support staff	213	17.4		
Other	51	4.2		
Industry				
Healthcare	178	14.5		
Finance and Banking	98	8		
Construction	50	4.1		
Information Technology	133	10.8		
Manufacturing	68	5.5		
Wholesale and Retail	77	6.3		
Transport and Logistics	46	3.8		
Education	182	14.8		
Defence and Security	26	2.1		
Leisure, Travel and Tourism	17	1.4		
Third Sector	23	1.9		

Public Sector	86	7		
Energy, Utilities and Environment	24	2		
Hospitality	16	1.3		
Legal and Law Enforcement	33	2.7		
Other	169	13.8		
Physical health	1224		13.34	3.9
Psychological health	1224		23.06	7.69
WHO presenteeism	1227		3.77	0.58
ASSET productivity	1226		71.85	18.17

Email culture and social norms

Aim 1 was to descriptively report on workplace culture and social norms regarding email engagement behaviours. Data on survey questions regarding culture and social norms are displayed in Table 2. 57.3% of participants reported that they access work emails on their personal mobile phone, 57.5% reported that they have responsibility for one or more shared inboxes, and 64.1% of participants reported that they access emails whilst on annual leave. Additionally, 23.3% of participants agreed that there was an expectation in their workplace that they respond to emails outside of their normal working hours, while 60.5% indicated that it was common in their workplace for staff to respond to emails outside of their normal working hours. 36.5% of participants agreed that their line manager regularly emails them outside of their normal working hours. Data on use of video calls, instant messaging and social media to communicate with colleagues outside of normal working hours is also displayed in Table 2.

Table 2
Summary of variables related to workplace email culture

	Yes		No		Is		Is not		Don't know	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Do you have access to work emails on your personal mobile phone?	701	57.3	523	42.7						
Do you have access to/responsibility for one or more shared inboxes?	701	57.5	519	42.5						
Do you access work emails when on annual leave?	785	64.1	440	35.9						
Is your job making a meaningful contribution to the world?	749	61	218	17.8	260	21.2				
To what extent do you find your job personally fulfilling?	280	22.9	641	52.4	241	19.7	61	5		
There is an expectation in my workplace that I respond to emails outside of my normal working hours	276	22.7	453	36.9	210	17.1	221	18	65	5.3

It is common within my workplace for staff to respond to emails outside of their normal working hours	88	7.2	229	18.7	167	13.6	556	45.3	187	15.2
My line manager regularly emails me outside of my normal working hours	211	17.2	383	31.2	186	15.1	357	29.1	91	7.4
	Yes		No							
	N	%	N	%						
Use video calls with colleagues outside of normal working hours	396	32.2	833	67.8						
Use instant messaging with colleagues outside of normal working hours	934	76	295	24						
Use social media to communicate with colleagues outside of normal working hours	432	35.2	797	64.8						

Table 3
Descriptive data on email volume, engagement, importance, overload and management tactics

	N	M	SD	Range
Email volume				
Number of emails received in past 24 hours	1202	37.74	52.23	0–724
Number of emails received in past 24 hours outside of normal working hours	1197	10.29	20.86	0–400
Email engagement				
Number of emails read and/or sent in past 24 hours	1207	46.38	53.57	0–530
Number of emails read and/or sent in past 24 hours outside of normal working hours	1208	6.38	13.33	0–150
Email work importance score	1226	3.92	0.89	1–5
Email management tactics				
Filing emails	1216	2.87	0.98	1–5
Managing tasks	1215	3.89	0.69	1–5
Email overload	1229	2.42	0.67	1–4.71

Table 3 displays the data regarding self-reported email volume and email engagement, during and outside of normal working hours, as well as the email work importance score, email management tactics (filing emails and managing tasks subscale scores) and email overload scores. Mean email volume (emails received in past 24 hour period) outside of normal working hours was 10.29 ($SD = 20.86$, range = 0–400), whereas the mean email engagement (emails read and sent in past 24 hour period) outside of normal working hours was 6.38 ($SD = 13.33$, range = 0–150). The mean email work importance score was 3.92 ($SD = 0.89$, range = 1–5), indicating that participants rated emails as important for their work. Participants indicated that they were, on average, moderately overloaded by emails ($M = 2.42$, $SD = 0.67$, range = 1–4.71). Participants also indicated moderate use of email management tactics: filing emails subscale ($M = 2.87$, $SD = 0.98$, range 1–5) and managing tasks subscale ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 0.69$, range = 1–5).

Email overload was negatively associated with the filing emails subscale ($r = -0.168$, $p < 0.001$) indicating that more proactive filing of emails was associated with reduced feelings of email overload. Additionally, feelings of email overload were associated with poorer physical ($r = 0.290$, $p < 0.001$) and psychological health ($r = 0.390$, $p < 0.001$), and lower productivity ($r = -0.244$, $p < 0.001$). Our two measures of productivity (the WHO presenteeism scale and the ASSET productivity item) were highly correlated ($r = 0.588$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 4. Predictors of email engagement outside of normal working hours

	Standardised Beta	<i>p</i>
Email work importance	0.172	<0.001 Adjusted R ² = 0.106
Email overload	0.176	<0.001 Adjusted R ² = 0.108
Filing emails	0.035	0.241 Adjusted R ² = 0.010

Email engagement outside of normal working hours

To address aim 3 of the study, we constructed three regression models with email engagement outside of normal working hours as the dependent variable, and email work importance, email overload, and the filing emails subscale as the independent variables. The main results of these models are shown in Table 4 (full models including confounding variables are displayed in Supplementary Table 4). Email work importance and email overload were both positively associated with email engagement outside of normal working hours (standardised beta = 0.172, $p < 0.001$ and standardised beta = 0.176, $p < 0.001$ respectively). This indicates that those participants who rated emails as highly important for completion of their work tasks, and/or those who felt overloaded by their emails, were more likely to engage with their work emails outside of normal working hours, which supports hypothesis 1. However, the degree to which participants file emails was not associated with email engagement outside of normal working hours, which does not support hypothesis 2. Across the three models, age was positively associated with email engagement outside of normal working hours, indicating that older participants are more likely to engage with work emails during leisure time. Similarly, position level was also associated with engaging with emails during leisure time. Those participants in more senior roles (i.e., who self-identified as an executive or senior staff) reported more engagement with work emails outside of working hours. It is possible that these two associations are related, because older participants may be more likely to be in senior roles.

Associations between email engagement outside of normal working hours and health and productivity

The third aim of the study was to test associations between email engagement outside of normal working hours and health and productivity. The main results of four regression models are displayed in Table 5 (full models including confounding variables are displayed in Supplementary Tables 5 and 6). Engagement with work emails during leisure time was associated with poorer physical health (standardised beta = 0.167, $p < 0.001$) and psychological health (standardised beta = 0.149, $p < 0.001$), however was not associated with presenteeism or productivity. Thus, hypothesis 3 was partly supported. Gender was associated with physical health (standardised beta = 0.230, $p < 0.001$) and psychological health (standardised beta = 0.194, $p < 0.001$), whereby women reported poorer physical and psychological health than men (physical health: women mean = 14.17, $SD = 3.82$, men mean = 12.34, $SD = 3.77$, psychological health: women mean = 24.48, $SD = 7.59$, men mean = 21.36, $SD = 7.43$). Age was positively associated with productivity (standardised beta = 0.108, $p < 0.001$) and presenteeism (standardised beta = 0.172, $p < 0.001$), indicating that older participants self-reported higher productivity levels.

Table 5

Associations of email engagement outside of normal working hours with physical health, psychological health, and productivity

Dependent variable = Physical Health			Dependent variable = Psychological Health			Dependent variable = Presenteeism			Dependent variable = Productivity		
	Standardised Beta	<i>p</i>									
Email engagement outside of normal working hours	0.167	<.001	Email engagement outside of normal working hours	0.149	<.001	Email engagement outside of normal working hours	-0.039	0.213	Email engagement outside of normal working hours	0.000	0.992
Adjusted $R^2 = 0.068$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.057$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.042$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.016$		
Email overload	0.317	<.001	Email overload	0.435	<.001	Email overload	-0.368	<.001	Email overload	-0.282	<.001
Adjusted $R^2 = 0.137$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.236$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.163$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.084$		

Associations between email overload and health and productivity

In correlation analysis, email overload was strongly correlated with physical health, psychological health, presenteeism and performance (see Supplementary Table 2). We therefore conducted an exploratory analysis, which was not pre-registered, to examine associations in regression analyses between email overload and physical health, psychological health, productivity and presenteeism. Results of these exploratory regression analyses are presented in Table 6. These analyses show that feeling overloaded by emails was associated with poorer physical health (standardised beta = 0.304, $p < 0.001$), psychological health (standardised beta = 0.426, $p < 0.001$), increased presenteeism (standardised beta = -0.361, $p < 0.001$) and reduced productivity (standardised beta = -0.275, $p < 0.001$).

Table 6
 Associations of email overload with physical health, psychological health, and productivity

Dependent variable = Physical Health			Dependent variable = Psychological Health			Dependent variable = Presenteeism			Dependent variable = Productivity		
	Standardised Beta	p		Standardised Beta	p		Standardised Beta	p		Standardised Beta	p
Age	-0.067	0.022	Age	-0.074	0.008	Age	0.200	<0.001	Age	0.131	<0.001
Gender	0.214	<0.001	Gender	0.194	<0.001	Gender	0.026	0.353	Gender	0.003	0.926
Ethnicity	-0.033	0.246	Ethnicity	-0.034	0.207	Ethnicity	0.009	0.749	Ethnicity	0.009	0.765
Employment type	0.004	0.879	Employment type	0.028	0.283	Employment type	-0.034	0.225	Employment type	-0.041	0.157
Position level	0.045	0.116	Position level	0.068	0.013	Position level	-0.005	0.862	Position level	-0.028	0.343
Industry	0.037	0.184	Industry	0.023	0.384	Industry	-0.020	0.472	Industry	0.008	0.782
Email overload	0.304	<0.001	Email overload	0.426	<0.001	Email overload	-0.361	<0.001	Email overload	-0.275	<0.001
Adjusted $R^2 = 0.131$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.205$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.140$			Adjusted $R^2 = 0.074$		

DISCUSSION

This study, of over 1,200 UK-based employees, provides the first evidence and complementary dataset on social norms and work-place culture around engagement with work emails outside of normal working hours. Additionally, we pre-registered and tested several hypotheses regarding motivations for engaging with work emails outside of normal working hours, and the associations of these behaviours with health and productivity. This is a particularly timely piece of research because the world of work has changed in the post-COVID era, with a greater move towards flexible and remote working (Felstead & Reuschke, 2020; ONS, 2022) which may result in increased work-home interference (Felstead & Henseke, 2017; Mann & Holdsworth, 2003). Additionally, large companies (e.g. Volkswagen, Daimler), and even countries (e.g. France) have introduced policy and legislation regarding employee engagement with work emails during leisure time with the aim of improving health and productivity, despite the lack of existing evidence on associations of these email engagement behaviours with health and productivity. Thus, the data presented here may be used as evidence for organisational policy change and guidance regarding employee email engagement, and a springboard for future research on this topic.

Critically, we provide descriptive data on employees from across many industries regarding organisational email culture and social norms. Perhaps unsurprisingly, over half of our sample report using their personal mobile phone to access work emails, which is likely to make it very difficult for employees to psychologically 'detach' from work. We know that time to rest and recover from work during the evening hours is critical for maintaining health and well-being over the long term (Dey & Rejojo-Howell, 2021; Sonnentag, 2001, 2003). Thus, instant and constant access to work emails via a personal mobile device may increase WHI and have a detrimental impact on health and productivity. Similarly, over half of our sample also indicated that they access work emails whilst on annual leave; and perhaps easy access to work emails on a personal mobile phone encourages and enables this behaviour. Thus, interventions that prohibit engagement with work emails outside of working hours may be beneficial in boosting employee health and productivity, though a fully powered randomised controlled trial is required to test this hypothesis. However, an additional factor to consider may be that some employees experience a positive emotional response from 'staying on top of' their inbox during weekends and whilst on annual leave, and the prospect of returning to an unintended inbox that has been accumulating emails over an extended period of time may be somewhat anxiety-inducing for some individuals. This is indicated in the current sample by more proactive filing behaviours being linked to reduced feelings of email overload. These findings point to the challenge of applying the JD-R model (Demerouti et al., 2001; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004) as a framework to understand the impact of engaging with email and its effects on health, as individual differences mean that emails can be seen as both a demand (e.g., I need to check my email on leave) and a resource (e.g., I can keep on top of my work at a time that suits me). Understanding when, and where, email use becomes a resource rather than a demand is an area worthy of further research.

The current study also highlights how importance placed on emails and feelings of email overload are positively associated with increased email engagement. The pressures to engage with work emails during leisure time may be determined by organisational culture. In our sample, almost two thirds of employees indicated that it is common in their workplace for colleagues to respond to emails outside of normal working hours. Additionally, almost a quarter stated that there is an expectation to be responsive to emails during leisure time, and over a third reported that their line manager regularly emails them outside of their normal working hours. Thus, a key motivation for employees to access their emails during leisure time may be because of expectations (whether consciously or not) set by the line manager. These expectations and practises can be viewed as social norms for the workplace, which can exacerbate the negative impact of WHI that is well documented in the literature to increase stress, determine health, reduce overall life satisfaction and decrease performance (Amstad et al., 2011; Butts et al., 2013). The present study further adds to this, suggesting that over engagement with work emails was associated with both worse physical and psychological health, while feelings of being overloaded were associated additionally with increased presentism and lower self-rated productivity.

Prior research focusing solely on the use of smart phone technology (Derks et al., 2015), has linked the influence of social norms on increased pressure to the boundary theory (Kreiner et al., 2009). The theory suggests that individuals engage effort in constructing and maintaining personal boundaries including a home-work border. When the border between home and work becomes blurred, interference can occur. In order to challenge existing social norms regarding availability of

employees outside of the work-place, the theory suggests boundaries need to be socially shared and in turn institutionalised to the point where the boundaries themselves become part of workplace culture. Organisations often do not often provide clear policies, guidance or training regarding work life balance (McDowall & Kinman, 2017). If these boundaries were introduced, this could be the first step towards socially sharing and strengthening the work-home border, although this process is considered an on-going negotiation which both the individual and organisation should engage with.

As evidenced by the current results, several individual differences may moderate the level of engagement with emails outside of working hours, which may disrupt how well boundaries can be broadly institutionalised. Thus, a “one size fits all” approach to organisational policy on email engagement during leisure time might not be appropriate and have unintended negative consequences. Firstly, the current study highlights how age influences engagement with work emails, with age being positively linked to increased email engagement and increased productivity. Differences between engagement in different age groups may be due to changing attitudes towards working culture and a difference in the perceived levels of resources available to engage fully in work (Kim & Kang, 2017). On the other hand, women demonstrate worse physical and psychological health than men in the current sample, which echoes those results gained from the recent Covid-19 pandemic. Women workers are historically disproportionately burdened by both work and childcare duties were found to have worse wellbeing (Bhumika, 2020; Platts et al., 2022) and productivity over the course of the pandemic (Etheridge et al., 2020), where WHI was indicated as high. These results accompany those indicating the need for different strategies for email management, and highlight the need for more research on individual motivations for email engagement and management during leisure time.

LIMITATIONS

First, the study did not directly monitor email engagement behaviour, instead focusing on the collection of self-report measures at one occasion. Although prior research has accomplished the measurement of direct behaviour using diary entry methods (Derks et al., 2015), given the current sample size the chosen methodology was deemed appropriate in order to gather a large amount of responses. The current study did also not measure existing workplace strategies aimed at reducing WHI or overload, future research could seek to understand if strategies of this nature exist to assess the moderating impact these have on out of hours email engagement. Finally, demands and resources were not assessed in the present study and future work could consider whether emails are perceived as a demand, or a resource, to individuals and how this may change across people, job roles and career stage.

Conclusions and implications for the workplace

The current paper presents a fully powered investigation into the impact of email engagement during leisure time and aspects of employee health and productivity. To the authors knowledge, this is the first study to directly examine this link, and through strong sampling and methods displays the real-life impact of email engagement on employees. We demonstrate social norms related to email engagement, and that engagement itself is associated with health and wellbeing. This indicates the importance of organisational wide changes in the communication of out of hours work engagement, but also the individual differences that could modify engagement and the impact this has. Future research could seek to implement strategies to increase work-home boundaries and test the impact of these strategies through rigorous trial methods.

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